

Data

1. Location of soil investigation

2. Soil Stratification

3. Soil Properties

Soil Properties			BH-02		BH-03		
			0.0 – 2.0	2.0 – 5.5	0.0 – 2.0	2.0 – 5.5	
Condition 2	Unit weight (γ)	gr/cm ³	1.87	2.05	1.75	2.02	
	Triaxial test	c	kPa	12.00	-	13.00	-
		ϕ	°	20.00	-	20.00	-
	Direct shear test	c	kPa	-	44.00	-	47.00
		ϕ	°	-	13.00	-	13.00
	Poisson ratio	μ_s		0.350	0.310	0.350	0.300
Modulus of elasticity Es	ton/m ²		8640	19200	8640	19200	
Condition 3	Unit weight (γ)	gr/cm ³	1.87	1.83	1.75	1.80	
	Triaxial test	c	kPa	12.00	-	13.00	-
		ϕ	°	20.00	-	20.00	-
	Direct shear test	c	kPa	-	41.00	-	42.00
		ϕ	°	-	11.00	-	11.00
	Poisson ratio	μ_s		0.350	0.330	0.350	0.320
Modulus of elasticity Es	ton/m ²		8160	17760	8160	17760	
Condition 4	Unit weight (γ)	gr/cm ³	1.87	1.72	1.75	1.69	
	Triaxial test	c	kPa	12.00	-	13.00	-
		ϕ	°	20.00	-	20.00	-
	Direct shear test	c	kPa	-	37.00	-	36.00
		ϕ	°	-	8.00	-	8.00
	Poisson ratio	μ_s		0.350	0.340	0.350	0.330
Modulus of elasticity Es	ton/m ²		7200	14400	7200	14400	
Condition 5	Unit weight (γ)	gr/cm ³	1.87	1.65	1.75	1.63	
	Triaxial test	c	kPa	12.00	-	13.00	-
		ϕ	°	20.00	-	20.00	-
	Direct shear test	c	kPa	-	30.00	-	28.00
		ϕ	°	-	5.00	-	5.00
	Poisson ratio	μ_s		0.350	0.350	0.350	0.350
Modulus of elasticity Es	ton/m ²		5280	9600	5280	9600	

Plaxis Output

1. Condition 1 – original condition

2. Condition 2

Degradation 0.5 m

Degradation 1.0 m

Degradation 1.5 m

Degradation 2.0 m

Degradation 2.5 m

3. Condition 3

Degradation 0.5 m

Degradation 1.0 m

Degradation 1.5 m

Degradation 2.0 m

Degradation 2.5 m

4. Condition 4

Degradation 0.5 m

Degradation 1.0 m

Degradation 1.5 m

Degradation 2.0 m

Degradation 2.5 m

5. Condition 5

Degradation 0.5 m

Degradation 1.0 m

Degradation 1.5 m

Degradation 2.0 m

Degradation 2.5 m